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Effects Of Gagne's Nine Events Of Instruction On Biology Students' Academic Achievement, Retention And Interest In Delta North Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction on Biology students' academic achievement in Delta North Senatorial District. The persistent decline in students' performance in Biology, as reported by WAEC Chief Examiners, and the continuous use of teacher-centred lecture methods despite curriculum recommendations for student-centred strategies, necessitated the study. Guided by Information Processing Theory, the study adopted a quasi-experimental design involving SS2 Biology students exposed to selected topics; digestive system, transport system, and respiratory system. The experimental group was taught using Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction while the control group received instruction through the lecture method. The population of the study consisted of 28, 324 SSII biology students. Using stratified simple random sampling technique, 203 SSII Biology students from six different schools participated in the study. Data collected were analyzed using Biology Achievement Test (BAT) which was validated by three specialists. The reliability coefficient of BAT was calculated using kuder Richardson 21 formula and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. Biology Achievement Test was administered as pretest before treatment and as a posttest after. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while independent sample t-test and ANCOVA were used to test hypothesis. Findings of the study revealed that students taught using Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction achieved significantly higher academic scores compared to those taught with the lecture method. Sex did not significantly influence students' achievement and no significant interaction effect was found between method and sex on the measured variables. The study concluded that Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction is a superior and more effective instructional strategy for improving biology learning outcomes. It was recommended that Biology teachers adopt Gagne's instructional model to enhance students' achievement.

Keywords: Gagne's Nine Event of Instruction, lecture method, biology students achievement, sex.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the bedrock of civilization, an instrument of change, social progress and meaningful living. It is an indispensable tool for the progress and sustainable development of any nation. Indeed, the survival of any individual and the society in general, depends largely on the type and quality of education the individual has been able to acquire. The growth and development of a society is also dependent on its educational system. Schooling is expected to speed up the education of people, thereby bringing about a more enriched civilization and development of the nation. One of the subjects taught during the schooling

process is Biology. Biology occupies a high-ranking position among the secondary school subjects in Nigeria. Biology, the study of living organisms, is taught in all senior secondary schools in Nigeria and records the highest enrollment among both science-inclined and arts-based students (Nwosu, 2016). According to Nwosu, the subject serves as a foundation for equipping learners with the skills to apply scientific concepts and principles to address everyday life challenges. There are advances recorded in fields such as Biochemistry, Physiology, Ecology, Genetics and Molecular biology that have made the subject a central focus in most human activities including problems like food scarcity, pollution, over population, radiation, disease, health, hygiene, family life, management and conservation of natural resources as well as Biotechnology and Ethics (Agboghoroma and Oyovwi, 2015). According to Ikeobi (2018) all form of human endeavors and absolutely nothing goes on in science without the application of Biology. It is impossible to overstate the significance and function of biology.

The teaching and learning of Biology in Nigerian secondary schools has not been optimal. According to Akpan (2018), students are faced with a lot of difficulties in Biology topics due to language and curriculum factors coupled with teacher characteristics, teaching methods, institutional and student embedded factors plus societal attitudes leading to poor performance in the subject. The inability to effectively grasp Biology concepts often at times leaves the student with no other option than to engage in rote memorization. A good performance in Biology is generally regarded as a prerequisite for entry into some highly skilled professions in science, technology, and industry, necessary for national development. Continuous poor performance in Biology, evident in both school-based assessments and national examinations, highlights the urgent need for more effective teaching approaches. These methods should enable students to deeply understand Biology concepts and apply them confidently during exams.

In recent years, various stakeholders in Nigerian society have expressed concerns about declining educational standards. Results from the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO) show a consistent downward trend in student performance (WAEC Examiner Report, 2023), with science subjects—particularly Biology—being especially affected. This ongoing challenge hinders Nigeria's efforts to build a strong scientific and technological foundation.

Effective teaching and learning of Biology require a critical examination of current instructional practices. Research suggests that inadequate student outcomes in science, including Biology, may stem largely from the teaching methods employed (Ariyo, 2016). From observations and practical experience, the traditional lecture method remains the dominant approach in Biology classes at the senior secondary level. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the impact of implementing Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction as an alternative teaching strategy in Biology.

The lecture method has been widely criticized as ineffective, monotonous, and uninspiring. As a result, there is a growing need for teachers to adopt and assess student-centered pedagogical approaches. These strategies allow learners to actively explore and interact with their subject matter while giving instructors the chance to carefully prepare and structure lessons for more meaningful delivery.

One prominent student-centered teaching approach is Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction. Gagne's nine events of instruction is referred to as a structured approach to teaching based on the "Nine Events of Instruction" developed by Educational Psychologist Robert Gagné, which outlines a specific sequence of steps to effectively deliver learning content, including gaining attention, stating objectives, activating prior knowledge, presenting new material, providing guidance, eliciting performance, giving feedback, assessing learning outcomes and enhancing retention and transfer. Gagné's instructional design model rests on the principle that learning occurs in a hierarchical manner, where foundational knowledge and skills progressively support the development of more advanced ones. His Nine Events of Instruction are specifically structured to facilitate this progression, with each step playing a vital role in creating an effective learning experience.

As noted by Agboghoroma, Bebenimibo, and Akpokiniovo (2022), Gagné's learning hierarchy provides educators with a clear, sequential framework for delivering instruction. Each stage addresses a specific type of cognitive processing that aids knowledge acquisition. Upon successfully completing each phase,

learners demonstrate active engagement, leading to improved retention and mastery of the targeted concepts and skills.

The nine steps include: (i) gaining attention, (ii) informing learners of the objectives, (iii) stimulating recall of prior knowledge, (iv) presenting the stimulus material, (v) providing learning guidance, (vi) eliciting performance, (vii) providing feedback, (viii) assessing performance, and (ix) enhancing retention and transfer.

A key benefit of Gagné's hierarchy for students lies in its ability to strengthen problem-solving abilities, promote long-term retention, and facilitate practical application of Biology concepts. Simha (2020) highlighted the superiority of this approach compared to traditional lecturing. This advantage is particularly evident in enhanced student outcomes related to academic achievement, knowledge retention, attitudes toward learning, and skills in applying principles and solving problems, as demonstrated in physics education (Agboghroma et al., 2022).

Gagné's model of Nine Instructional Events aims to facilitate deep mastery of subject matter and competencies by dividing the learning journey into digestible, sequential phases. Through structured support and direction at each stage, educators can enable learners to construct their understanding and abilities in a logical, efficient way.

In the context of Biology, academic performance is typically measured by the marks or grades students earn on tests following instruction. More broadly, it reflects how successfully learners, educators, or schools meet defined educational objectives, whether immediate or extended. It signals the degree to which individuals have accomplished their targeted learning outcomes, often evidenced by milestones like degree completion, and is commonly evaluated via exams or ongoing evaluations.

Researchers like Akinyele (2021) have noted widespread worry among parents, school leaders, teachers, psychologists, and guidance counselors regarding secondary students' academic results. Persistent underperformance in science disciplines, particularly Biology, remains a significant issue for stakeholders in science education (Ariyo, 2016). Given that all school-based teaching efforts ultimately target improved learner outcomes, exploring innovative approaches is essential. This justifies investigating how Gagné's nine events influence Biology students' performance levels in the Delta North Senatorial District. Quality teaching approaches should enhance participation and outcomes equally for all learners, irrespective of gender. Gender refers to whether an individual is male or female. Eryilmaz (2014) suggested that gender influences attitudes and performance in Biology. Societal expectations, shaped through socialization, contribute to these patterns. Enrollment and achievement gaps between males and females in Biology and broader sciences highlight gender disparities. Early educational sociology focused on explaining lower female attainment across levels. Biology classes include both male and female learners with distinct traits influenced by biology, potentially leading to performance differences observed in some studies. Given Biology's societal importance and the mixed-gender classroom environment, identifying inclusive methods that elevate performance, recall, and engagement without gender bias is crucial. This study, therefore, examines the effects of implementing Gagné's nine events on Biology students' performance, retention, and interest in the Delta North Senatorial District.

Statement of the problem

The WAEC Chief Examiners' reports for Biology in the May/June Senior School Certificate Examinations (2018–2023) noted that candidates' overall performance showed no substantial departure from earlier patterns but revealed a gradual year-on-year deterioration.

Curriculum guidelines and educational specialists have repeatedly endorsed the adoption of learner-centred instructional strategies for science subjects, including Biology. However, evidence from classroom practice indicates that Biology educators predominantly favour traditional teacher-directed approaches, especially direct lecturing, possibly owing to its straightforward execution.

In response, science education scholars have pursued accessible and effective alternatives capable of elevating students' academic outcomes, reinforcing knowledge retention, stimulating sustained engagement, and minimising gender-related disparities in Biology performance, recall, and motivation. Given the fundamental differences between Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction and conventional lecturing in lesson organisation and delivery, empirical examination of its efficacy is warranted.

Accordingly, this study addresses the following research problem: What impact does the implementation of Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction have on senior secondary school students' academic achievement, knowledge retention, and interest in Biology within the Delta North Senatorial District.

Purpose of the study

The primary aim of this study was to investigate the impact of Gagne's Nine Event of Instruction on senior secondary biology students' academic achievement in Delta North senatorial More specifically, the study aimed to:

1. determine whether there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores between biology students taught using Gagne's Nine Event of Instruction and those taught via the Lecture method.
2. examine differences in mean achievement scores between male and female Biology students under each teaching method (Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction versus lecture method).
3. analyse the interaction effect of teaching method and gender on Biology students' achievement.

Research questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. Is there a significant difference in mean achievement scores between Biology students taught using Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction and those taught via the lecture method in senior secondary schools in the Delta North Senatorial District?
2. Is there a significant sex difference in mean achievement scores among Biology students exposed to Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction versus the lecture method in senior secondary schools in the Delta North Senatorial District?
3. What is the interaction effect of teaching method and gender on Biology students' achievement in senior secondary schools in the Delta North Senatorial District?

Hypothesis

Three hypothesis guided the study:

HO₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores between Biology students taught using Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction and those taught via the lecture method.

HO₂: There is no significant sex difference in mean achievement scores among Biology students exposed to either Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction or the lecture method.

HO₃: There is no significant interaction effect between teaching method and gender on Biology students' achievement.

METHODS

The study was quasi-experimental in nature involving pre-test and post-test of non-equivalent control group design. The design was deemed suitable as it did not involve randomization of samples. Instead, intact class was used to ensure that school activity was not disrupted. The study comprised of two groups; experimental group and lecture method group. Both experimental and lecture groups were taught the same Biology concepts. The only difference between the two groups was their teaching method. The experimental group was taught using Gagne's Nine Event of Instruction strategy while the control group was taught using using lecture method. A pre-test was administered to both groups before treatment. A post-test was then administered at the conclusion of the treatment.

The effect of the two methods were compared. The population of this study comprised 28,324 biology students in public senior secondary schools two (SSII) in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

The choice of SSII Biology students was because they would not be involved in external examination. The study included a total of 203 SSII biology students from six mixed and single public secondary school in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State. The selection of these schools was based on simple random sampling technique. Simple random sampling technique was used to ensure equal probability of selection of all schools in Delta North Senatorial District, Delta State.

In this study, Biology Achievement Test was used for data collection. The face validity of the BAT was established by three experts which comprised an experienced biology teacher, science educator and measurement and evaluation lecturer. The content validity of the BAT was done by using a table of

specification based on Bloom's taxonomy to ensure that contents were rightly represented. The reliability of the BAT was determined through utilization of Kuder Richardson 21 formula. The BAT was administered on 45 Biology students in a senior secondary school in Ika North East Local Government Area of Delta State. These students were not included in the study's target population. The student responses were evaluated and the scores were analyzed using Kuder Richardson 21 formula, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.82. The treatment consisted of teaching students in separate groups using Gagne's Nine Event of Instruction and Lecture method. pretest using BAT was conducted before the treatment followed by a posttest at the end of the treatment. The acquired scores were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and the hypotheses was tested using independent sample t-test and ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in the mean achievement scores among biology students exposed to Gagne's Nine Event of instruction and lecture method in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District?*

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing the difference between the achievement score of students' taught Biology with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method

Groups	N	Mean	Mean Difference	SD
Gagne	111	36.97	11.63	4.21
Lecture	92	25.34		6.44

Table 1 shows that the biology students taught with Gagne's nine events of instruction had a mean score of 36.97 with a standard deviation of 4.21 and those taught with lecture method obtained a mean score of 25.34 with a standard deviation of 6.44. There is a mean difference of 11.63 between the two groups in favour of the Gagne's nine events of instruction. To determine if the difference is significant, H_{02} was tested.

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores among Biology students exposed to Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction and Lecture Method in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District.

To determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test H_{02} independent sample t-test statistics was used to analyzed their pre-test scores and the result is shown in 2.

Table 2: Independent sample statistics determining the difference between the achievement of biology students taught with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method at pre-test

Groups	N	Mean	Mean SD Diff	df	tcal	Sig(2-tailed)
Gagne	111	15.49	1.22	3.83	201	1.639 0.103
Lecture	92	14.27		4.27		

Table 2 shows that the difference is not significant since the calculated sig value of 0.103 which is greater than 0.05 alpha level of significant was obtained with this, independent sample t-test becomes the appropriate statistics to be used to test H_{02} and the result is shown in Table 3

Table 3: Independent sample t-test statistics comparing the difference between the achievement of students' taught Biology with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method

Groups	N	Mean	Mean Difference	SD	df	tcal	Sig(2-tail)
Gagne	111	36.97	11.63	4.21	201	15.47	0.00
Lecture	92	25.34		6.44			

Table 3 shows that the difference is significant since the calculated sig value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05 alpha level of significant was obtained with this, H_{02} which states that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores among Biology students exposed to Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction and Lecture Method in Senior Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District was rejected.

Research Question two: *What is the difference in mean achievement score of male and female students taught Biology using Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction and lecture method?*

Table 4: Descriptive statistics showing the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students' taught Biology with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method

Groups	Sex	N	Mean	Mean Difference	SD
Gagne	Male	61	36.67	0.67	3.99
	Female	50	37.34		4.47
Lecture	Male	20	23.45	2.41	5.95
	Female	72	25.86		6.51

Table 4 shows that the male biology students taught with Gagne's nine events of instruction had a mean score of 36.67 with a standard deviation of 3.99 and the female biology students obtained a mean score of 37.34 with a standard deviation of 4.47. There is a mean difference of 0.67 between the two groups in favour of the males. Also for the lecture group, the male biology students had a mean score of 23.45 with a standard deviation of 5.95 and the female biology students obtained a mean score of 25.86 with a standard deviation of 6.51. There is a mean difference of 2.41 in favour of the females. To determine if the difference is significant, H_{02} was tested.

H_{02} : there is no significant difference in mean achievement score of male and female students taught Biology using Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction and lecture method

To determine the appropriate statistics to be used to test H_{02} the students pre-test scores were tested using independent sample t-test statistics.

Table 5 : Independent sample statistics comparing the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students' taught Biology with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method at pretest

Groups	Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	df	tcal	Sig(2-tail)
Gagne	Male	61	14.98	0.11	3.42	109	1.539	0.127
	Female	50	16.10		4.23			
Lecture	Male	20	14.40	0.20	4.21	90	0.182	0.856
	Female	72	14.60		4.32			

Table 5 shows that the difference is not significant since the calculated sig value of 0.127 and 0.856 which is greater than 0.05 alpha level of significant was obtained for the male and female students in Gagne nine events of instruction and lecture groups respectively, With this, independent sample t-test statistics becomes the appropriate statistics to be used to test H_{02} and this is shown in table 6

Table 6: Independent sample t-test statistics comparing the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students' taught Biology with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method

Groups	Sex	N	Mean	Mean Diff	SD	df	tcal	Sig(2-tail)
Gagne	Male	61	36.67	0.67	3.99	109	0.831	0.408
	Female	50	37.34		4.47			
Lecture	Male	20	23.45	2.41	5.95	90	1.492	0.139
	Female	72	25.86		6.51			

Table 6 shows that the difference is not significant since the calculated sig value of 0.408 and 0.139 which is greater than 0.05 alpha level of significant was obtained for both males and female students taught with Gagne nine instructional events and lecture method respectively. With this, H_{02} which states that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female students Biology students taught with Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction and Lecture Method is not rejected.

Research Question three: *What is the interaction effect between methods and sex on Biology students' achievement?*

Table 7: Descriptive statistics showing the interaction effect between methods and sex on the achievement score of students' taught Biology with Gagne's nine events of instruction and lecture method

Groups	Sex	N	Mean	Mean Difference	SD
Gagne		111	36.97	11.63	4.21
Lecture		92	25.34		6.44
Gagne	Male	61	36.67	0.67	3.99
	Female	50	37.34		4.47
Lecture	Male	20	23.45	2.41	5.95
	Female	72	25.86		6.51

Table 7 shows that the biology students taught with Gagne's nine events of instruction had a mean score of 36.97 with a standard deviation of 4.21 and those taught with lecture method obtained a mean score of 25.34 with a standard deviation of 6.44. There is a mean difference of 11.63 between the two groups in favour of the Gagne's nine events of instruction. The table shows that the male biology students taught with Gagne's nine events of instruction had a mean score of 36.67 with a standard deviation of 3.99 and the female biology students obtained a mean score of 37.34 with a standard deviation of 4.47. There is a mean difference of 0.67 between the two groups in favour of the female. Also for the lecture group, the male biology students had a mean score of 23.45 with a standard deviation of 5.95 and the female biology students obtained a mean score of 25.86 with a standard deviation of 6.51. There is a mean difference of 2.41 in favour of the females. This shows that there is an interaction effect between methods and sex on biology students achievement. To determine if the interaction effect is significant, H_{03} was tested using ANCOVA statistics

H_{03} : There is no significant interaction effect between methods and sex on Biology students' achievement

Table 8: ANCOVA statistics comparing the interaction effect between methods and sex on students achievement

Source	Type III Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Corrected Model	9181.491	4	2454.623	179.3300.00	
Intercept	3626.583	1	3626.503	264.945	0.00
Pre-achievement	2904.045	1	2904.045	212.1630.00	
Groups	5081.287	1	5081.287	371.2280.00	
Sex	33.381	1	33.381	2.439	0.120
Group*Sex	67.963	1	67.963	4.965	0.027
Error	2910.179	198	16.034		
Total	216515.00	203			
Corrected Total	12528.670	202			

Table 8 shows a significant interaction effects between method and sex on achievement since the calculated significant value of 0. 027 which is less than the alpha value of 0.05 was obtained, with this, H_{03} , which states there is no significant interaction effect between methods and sex on achievement is rejected.

DISCUSSION

The first findings of the study showed a significant difference in the achievement of biology students taught with Gagne nine event of instruction and lecture method. On analysis of research question 1, Table 1 showed that students taught with Gagne nine event of instruction had a higher mean than those taught with lecture method. On testing the hypothesis, this difference was found to be significant as shown in Table 3. This differences could be as a variation in the mode of application of the different method. The Gagne nine even of instruction offer a systematic approach to designing effective instructional activities that cater for different cognitive processes and this must have made the teachers to adequately plan and prepare for the lesson in such a way that students are actively involved in the teaching and learning process unlike the lecture method group where the teacher is mostly the sole dispenser of knowledge. This findings agrees with the findings of Sharfaddeen et al. (2024) whose result showed a significant difference in performance between students taught using Gagne’s Nine Events of Instruction and those taught using lecture methods in favour of the Gagne’s Nine Events of Instruction.

The second finding of the study showed a non-significant difference in the achievement of male and female students taught with Gagne’s Nine Events of Instruction and those taught using lecture methods. On analysis of the research questions, the results on Table 4 showed that the males students taught with Gagne’s Nine Events of Instruction had a higher mean scores than the females while the female students had a higher mean scores than their male counter parts in the lecture method group. This differences were found not to be significant as shown in Table 6. This non-significant difference shows that both the male and female students benefitted almost equally from the teaching. This findings is in line with that of Sharfaddeen et al(2024) who found no significant difference between boys and girls taught with Gagne’s Nine Events of Instruction and those taught using lecture methods but disagrees with that of the Nwaobi (2017) whose finding showed that use of Gagne’s hierarchical learning strategy favours the male more than the female in biology achievement.

Also, the third finding of the study showed a significant effect of interaction between methods and sex on biology students’ achievement. This significant effect of interaction shows that the methods and sex combined to influence the student’s achievements when both methods were used. This could be as a result

of action of both the minds and hands on activities that the students were engaged in. This is an indication that these activities may be influenced by sex. This findings disagrees with the findings of Agboro-Eravwoke (2022), who found no significant interaction effect between method and sex on achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: Gagne's nine event of instruction strategy significantly improved students achievement in biology more than lecture method. Also Gagne's nine event of instruction did not significantly differentiate between male and female student achievement in biology.

RECOMMENDATION

In the light of the findings of the Study, the following recommendations are made to facilitate effective teaching and learning of biology.

1. Biology teachers should adopt the use of Gagne's nine event of instruction strategy in the teaching of biology since the method is found to improve student achievement, retention and interest.
2. Teacher training institution, such as colleges of education and universities should train student-teachers on the effective implementation of Gagne's Nine Event of Instruction strategy.
3. Workshops and seminars on the effective implementation of Gagne's nine event of instruction strategy should always be organized for teachers by the government so as to help them become competent in the use of this teaching strategy in the teaching and learning process.

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